

PUBLIC POLICY EXCEPTION IN INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION AND APPROACH OF PAKISTAN COURTS

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Abstract

The public policy exception in international commercial arbitration has been a controversial and inconsistently applied defense against the recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards. This article examines the approaches of various jurisdictions, including the United Kingdom, United States, Germany, Australia, Hong Kong, Canada, China, and Pakistan, in interpreting and applying the public policy exception under the New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards. The article traces the historical development of the regulatory framework for international commercial arbitration and the adoption of the New York Convention, which aimed to facilitate the recognition and enforcement of foreign arbitral awards with limited grounds for refusal. The article discusses the pro-enforcement policy of the Convention and the challenges posed by the public policy exception. It analyzes the different interpretations of public policy across jurisdictions, ranging from narrow and restrictive to broad and expansive. The article focuses on the approach of Pakistani courts, which have shifted towards a pro-enforcement stance in recent years, emphasizing the importance of upholding the finality and enforceability of arbitral awards. The article concludes that respect for party autonomy, the pro-enforcement policy, and the desire for finality should guide courts in applying a restrictive interpretation of the public policy exception, limiting its application to cases where the fundamental principles of morality and justice would be contravened.

INTRODUCTION

With states opening up to the regional trade and joint ventures, the increased demand of inclusion in international commercial contracts an arbitration clause needs no reiteration. Among other methods of alternative dispute's resolution, arbitration is an effective method which enables the parties for smooth running of international trade and commerce. Resolute in its brevity, an efficient and concise method of dispute settlement outside the national court system, selected by the parties for addressing

current or future conflicts, is referred to as arbitration. As many as four fundamental features of arbitration can be found from the foregoing which is enumerated hereinafter. Firstly, arbitration serves as a viable substitute to national court enabling parties to effectively transfer their disputes beyond the purview of domestic courts upon mutual consent. Secondly, an arbitration agreement, akin to any contract, is a inter parties affair, wherein they consent to resolve their conflict through a private procedure. Thirdly,

principle of party autonomy bestows upon the parties complete authority to ascertain system, structure, form and other particulars of the arbitration process. The parties retain full authority of their disputes' resolution by selecting arbitration unilaterally. Fourthly, the parties have concurred that arbitration will be the mechanism for dispute resolution and have committed to adhere to and execute the arbitral decision. The arbitrators' ruling is thus conclusive, final and binding on the parties (Lew, at al). The contracting parties for the aforementioned accounts prefer arbitration agreements to litigation. However, envisaged in the New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards adopted in 1958 ('Convention'58'), the public policy exception in contrast to its pro-enforcement policy ('PE Policy') has provided for the enforcement courts to deny foreign arbitral award ('award') the recognition and enforcement. In this context, public policy turns out to be one of the most controversial exceptions and when applied has led to inconsistency and unpredictability in decisions by courts. Therefore, it will be seen in due course of this writing the extent of said exception in various jurisdictions and how it has been applied by the courts in Pakistan.

The Article proceeds as follows. Part I explains what international commercial arbitration is and its essential characteristics. Part II traces the historical development of its regulatory scheme and how the evolution took place over the years along with its effect. Part III reviews the adoption of the Convention'58 and analyses the defences provided therein. Part IV discusses public policy approaches with respect to distinct jurisdictions. Part V provides for the approach and attitude of the courts in Pakistan when they are to adjudicate on the Exception.

International Commercial Arbitration

For resolution of disputes among parties, a private method it is the arbitration (Onyema, 2010). Equally so for international and domestic. Sufficient it is to be qualified as international should its subject matter, procedure or organization involves element of transcending national borders, or the parties originate from distinct legal systems, or there is a blend of these factors. The word international was traditionally

associated with arbitration encompassing attributes of both commercial and public international arbitration where parties from one country used to make investments in another and subsequent disputes between them involved international law issues due to state sovereignty implications (Lew, at al). With an aim of finality and binding, where nationals of two different jurisdictions privity to a contractual transaction accord to get their disputes resolved in a mutually agreed forum, such forum is referred to as international arbitration. It involves independent arbitrators who determines between the said nationals in relation to their disputes adopting procedures, structures and substantive legal or non-legal standards chosen directly or indirectly by the parties (Lew, at al). However, it remains to be seen as to what underlying transaction qualifies a commercial.

Article I of the UNCITRAL Model Law provides for its application to international commercial arbitration ('ICA'). The word 'commercial' is described in its footnote setting forth the criteria to broadly interpret the word to encompass issues stemming from all commercial connections, regardless of whether they are contractual. The use of the word 'include' while indicating the relationships of a commercial nature makes the term commercial inclusive giving two-fold advantages. Firstly, the international business community is offered the flexibility and adaptability that see its needs met. Secondly, the states can utilize it in situations where they lack a specialized set of commercial laws for international business.

The Convention'58 proposes a commercial characterization and reservation grounded in national law, as evidenced by Article I (3), which grants signatory states the authority to stipulate that the convention will apply solely to matters deemed commercial under their respective national laws (Anusornsen, 2012). The rationale proposed for this commercial reservation is the adherence to the Convention'58 for civil law jurisdictions, which differentiates between business and non-business transactions (Lew et al.).

Speaking of its forms, that is, *ad hoc* and institutional, the same depends on a decision made by the parties during the insertion of the arbitration provision. In the first scenario, parties without an institutional arbitration set up their own system for resolving a

specific agreement or dispute. This includes deciding on how to start the process, selecting the arbitrators (and how many), and setting the rules for the procedure. The parties concerned also get to decide which law is to govern the arbitration agreement and the arbitration process. Nevertheless, if no law under which arbitration proceedings would take place is chosen, either intentionally or otherwise, then the proceedings will be regulated by the laws where the arbitration occurs. Whereas, in the latter form, specialized arbitration institutions function under their own processes and regulations, where parties submit their issues for arbitration. The ICC and the LCIA are among the most commonly utilized and recognized arbitration institutions globally.

Historical Development

A longstanding system for settling conflicts that has been used in businesses is arbitration. In contrast to the current framework, arbitral procedures were previously unregulated by legal statutes. Rather, it was employed by members of trade and professional associations to resolve conflicts. Previously, seasoned business professionals would assist others within the association in resolving disputes that emerged during their commercial transactions, adhering to the conventions and practices of the specific trade association. The arbitrators issued a binding verdict that the defaulting party willingly adhered to. The compliance was mainly due to the fact that the conflicting parties, as members of the same trade organization, typically maintained ongoing business relationships and hence deemed compliance more commercially advantageous (Onyema, 2010).

For resolution of disputes relating to international trade, arbitration has always been afforded precedence over traditional court system for centuries by the commercial world. Nevertheless, the issue relating recognition and enforcement ('RAE') of arbitrators' decisions in ICA always remained a pressing concern mainly on two accounts. Firstly, the intervention in the arbitration process of national court and secondly, the arbitrators' decisions were reviewed given the absence of international regulation of arbitration. Hence, prior to enforcement by the national court of award passed by the arbitrators in international arbitration, its recognition was found contingent on

the national law and political factors of the country where the prevailing party seeks execution (Lew, at al). Nevertheless, it is apparent that the evolution of contemporary ICA was founded on national legislations, including the English law of 1698 pertaining to arbitration, the inclusion of arbitration in the French Code of Civil Procedure of 1806, and Federal Arbitration Act of 1925, which constituted an inaugural federal arbitration statute in the United States (Lew, at al).

To facilitate ICA and establish a governing structure for RAE of an award, two Hague Conventions were enacted in 1899 and 1907. They are known as The Hague Convention for the Pacific Settlement of International Disputes. It established the Permanent Court of Arbitration (Lew, at al). It was followed by the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) in 1919, and in 1923 it formed its Court of International Arbitration. This court was designed to offer a fair, independent and impartial system for resolving business disputes between individuals from various nations. The ICC significantly promoted and adopted Geneva Protocol on Arbitration Clauses in 1923 ("Protocol'23") and the Geneva Convention on the Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards in 1927 ("Convention'27"). The global acknowledgment of arbitration contracts and decisions were intended from the foregoing. However, the said instruments were bereft of their successful operation on account of double *exequatur*. An *exequatur* means leave or permission for enforcement and double *exequatur* essentially means that pursuant to enforcement of an award, its holder must demonstrate that it has attained 'final' status in both the jurisdictions where it was issued as well as where R&E is sought (Rowley, 2019). In other words, it was expected of the award to be tagged with finality within whose jurisdiction the same was issued prior to getting it enforced in the executing jurisdiction (Lew, at al). Requesting court permission used to open gateway for the unsuccessful party to question the decision of tribunal thus inviting the court to revisit the award. Besides, it would fall upon the winning party had to establish in enforcement jurisdiction that the arbitral panel and procedure conformed to local laws and complied with the enforcement regulations specified in the 1927 Convention. The Convention'58

however eliminated prior requirement of 'double *exequatur*' that was characteristic of the enforcement framework of the Geneva Convention (Rowley, 2019).

Effect of regulatory framework

In both national and intl. legal frameworks, a collection of regulations oversees the practice of arbitration to ensure its proper functioning and success. This legislative structure is essential for upholding arbitration agreements, providing an ordered arbitration procedure, and guaranteeing that arbitration rulings are final and enforceable. The arbitrations' legal framework provides parties with the discretion to establish the organization and management of their arbitration processes. The selection of a particular arbitration method signifies the parties' objectives and preferences. The choice to settle conflicts by arbitration arises from the parties' preferences, and the governing rules are likewise established according to their desires. Ultimately, the primary considerations are the parties' intentions and the necessity of ensuring that arbitration awards are effective and enforceable.

A unique process the international arbitration is that involves agreement imbued with international characteristic the resolution of any dispute of which is found in realm of impartial arbitrators chosen by the involved parties. This mechanism follows specific procedures and legal standards chosen by the parties, incorporating aspects like party autonomy, arbitration rules, and international conventions. Essential to this process is the agreement between parties, which dictates the rules and limits of the arbitration. The agreement may explicitly delineate the rules and processes to be followed or implicitly do so by designating the relevant arbitration rules. In the lack of consensus on specific rules or arbitration guidelines, the process of arbitration is governed, regulated and overseen by the law where it is taken place. The international conventions emphasize the significance of party autonomy within the regulatory framework, and not to mention the assurance that arbitration agreements and awards would see enforced.

Recognition and Enforcement Pursuant to Convention'58

Convention'58 was adopted to significantly enhance the proficiency of ICA by assuring the swift awards' enforcement in conformity with the parties' intentions (Lew, et al). It facilitated the enforcement of awards in accord with party autonomy (Tosun, 2019). Since succeeded by Protocol'23 and Convention'27, the Convention'58 presents a significant enhancement by facilitating a more straightforward process seeking RAE of awards (Redfern, et al). Further aimed that arbitration agreements are standardized and the signatory nations enforced the award in favour of the winning party (Anusornsena, 2012). In national legislation, Convention'58 was to be incorporated hence paving for awards their RAE with considerable ease and expediency. The fundamental criteria for an effective process in ICA was delineated in which domestic courts now fully acknowledge international arbitration agreements and awards. Consequently, courts' role in ICA has developed progressed to facilitate and improve the process of arbitration, as evidenced in the notion of 'pro-enforcement bias'. This bias underscores the legal system's commitment to respecting and facilitating the parties' choice to arbitrate, while also assuring that arbitration rulings are recognized and enforced with nominal judicial interference. The said intervention has been further circumscribed in Convention'58 with provision of limited enforcement refusal grounds therein hence, ensuring courts narrowly interpret those grounds so that certainty and predictability may be achieved globally.

The Convention'58 applies to the RAE of awards created in a country other than where the same is requested. The award must stem from disputes between individuals or entities, whether natural or legal. Additionally, an award not being a domestic within the seeking state is also included in Convention'58. Nevertheless, the application of Convention'58 is subject to two qualifications stipulated in A.I(3) thereof, namely, reciprocity reservation and commercial reservation (Redfern, et al). The former limits its applicability to awards only to those rendered in signatory member states to the Convention'58. As already discussed above, the latter

allows a country signing the agreement to restrict those disputes concerning legal relationships, both contractual and non-contractual, that are deemed commercial under its national law.

Article II (2) of the Convention'58 stipulates that a written and signed arbitration agreement is held to be valid, notwithstanding it be a contractual arbitral clause or as a distinct arbitration agreement. Besides, if the parties' intention to arbitrate the dispute is manifest from the documents and/or letters, then an arbitration agreement is so established. An award on its announcement by arbitrator(s) sees the arbitration proceedings concluded. The award grants the victorious party the right to pursue RAE in a state where the losing party has its asset/property. According to A.III, each contractual state is under obligation for RAE of award issued in other contracting state (Tang, 2014). In view of the foregoing Article, it is expected of states to recognize awards as binding, and enforce them in accordance with national law, provided they do not contravene the Convention'58 (Moses, 2008).

Since recognition is often cited by the losing party as defense, the meaning the term inheres and its distinction with the term 'enforcement' is made available here for complete understanding. Recognition is an initial step which is followed by enforcement in the State where RAE of an award is pursued. It pertains to same disputes that were previously addressed in arbitration proceedings before the tribunal, culminating in an award. It serves as a 'shield' against invites to revisit matters that already has culminated into resolution through arbitration (Ma, 2005). Recognition, as a form of estoppel, seeks to prohibit a party from introducing new issues or questions in the court of its State that have already been resolved by the tribunal when enforcement of the award is pursued (Redfern, et al). Unlike the word 'final' the Convention'27 used in its A.1(d), the Convention'58 employed the word 'binding' in Article V(1)(e) thereof for the award. The foregoing deviation represents the substantial improvement which envisages that the award is exempt not only from merit evaluation by the court to which it is presented for recognition but also from declaration of finality by the court that issued the award. In simple words, when an award is recognized by the court, it

acknowledges award is valid and binding, so granting it an impact akin to that of a court judgment (Moses, 2008). The court seems to only serve as an executing body when recognizing and enforcing the award, and is not allowed to challenge the award or review the evidence as an appellate court.

When in a contracting state a request before the court to enforce an award is made, not only recognition of its validity is expected of the court, but also award's execution is facilitated through any prescribed methods under the enforcing jurisdiction to recover the payable sum or to fulfill any directives specified in the award (Moses, 2008). The phrase 'RAE' of foreign award used in Convention'58, contrary to phrase 'recognition or enforcement' used in Geneva Convention 1927, reveals that award once recognized being valid and binding upon parties *inter se* will see its enforcement by the court (Redfern, et al). Perhaps, this also resolves as to why about Convention'58 recognition is said to serve a 'shield' and enforcement, conversely, a 'sword'. In this way, the Convention'58 exhibited considerable efficacy not only in the enforcement of arbitration agreements as well as the decisions rendered in terms thereof. For the reason that the grounds for refusing RAE are restricted, exhaustive, not merit-based, and the responsibility to prove does not rest with the individual pursuing RAE (Redfern, et al).

Overview of Refusal of Recognition and Enforcement

Defences available to the losing party to prevent RAE of an award are delineated in A. V of the Convention'58. Not less than final and binding, the courts very infrequently reverse an award. Contrary to be found getting challenged in the realm of merits, awards are primarily contested on regulatory grounds or allegations of arbitrator dishonesty or prejudice. Nevertheless, the unsuccessful can always resort to two avenues to contest the arbitral ruling. Firstly, to the court of the arbitration's situs because of supervisory jurisdiction over the arbitral proceedings, and secondly, where the award holder presents award in the court for RAE, to such court (Moses, 2008).

The first defence has two parts. The first one deals with the incapacity of part. The other one is the validity of agreement containing an arbitral clause or

an arbitration agreement on the touchstone of the law to which the parties have subjected it for. When no mention is found of any law in such agreement, then the law of the country where the award was made (Moses, 2008). The second defence pertains to the failure to issue the requisite notice on the arbitrator's appointment, of commencement by him the arbitration proceedings, or such party could not be otherwise put forward its case. Hence, ensuring procedural fairness, issuance of proper notice and undertaking of arbitration properly (Redfern, et al). Such issuance of the notice is akin to what is known as due process and affording the fair opportunity of hearing to all parties. Due process may include opportunities like participating in arbitration proceeding, producing evidence and raising objection to the procedural rulings of the arbitral tribunal (Iqbal, 2022). It may however be argued that as arbitration proceedings are the outcome of parties' consent, the fair hearing requirement may not be considered with similar standards as applied by the court of law in ordinary cases.

If an award rendered addresses a conflict not contemplated in the arbitration agreement by the parties to it, it will not be seeing its enforcement as per mandate of A. V(I)(c). It relates to jurisdictional issues such as acting in excess of authority and deciding disputes beyond the realm of reference before the arbitral tribunal (Redfern, et al). Since consent of the parties happens to be the source of arbitrator's authority, should such authority given specifically under the arbitration agreement is found to be transcending or exceeding, then the Convention'58 does not enforce any such consequent award (Moses, 2008). By invoking this defense, the losing party invites the competent authority to assess whether the award the RAE of which is under review is within the scope of the dispute or difference as defined by the terms of reference, or whether it addresses issues exceeding the parameters of the arbitral agreement. Nonetheless, the defence must be raised before the arbitral tribunal in initial stage of proceedings so as to prevent a party from the mischief of subsequent preclusion if asserted thereafter.

Next defence worded in Article V(I)(d) pertains to the very composition of the arbitral tribunal. It is the fourth ground of refusal of RAE of award. The party

opposing RAE of award is required to demonstrate the tribunal's composition does not conform to the agreement or is not regulated by the law of seat of the arbitration, in the absence of a specified governing law for the proceedings. While accepting the defence put forward by the losing party, the RAE of award may be refused in favour of the award holder.

Next in line is the defence that the award has not yet become binding, or has been set aside or suspended by a competent authority of the country in which, or under the law of which, that award was made. [Article V(I)(e)] Although the word 'binding' has not been defined in the Convention'58, yet it appears that an award is binding if there is no way to challenge the award on merits by way of filing the appeal before the court at the situs of arbitration to set aside or vacate the award because the law that governs the arbitration proceedings is the *lex arbitri* (Moses, 2008). The party pursuing RAE may contend that the losing party's denial to contest the award on its merits at the arbitration situs within the statute of limitations has rendered the award binding on the parties.

The remaining two defences are those that the enforcing court may consider *suo moto* (Redfern, et al). Provided in Article V (2) are lack of arbitrability and violation of public policy. Each state determines which disputes should be settled in court and which can be resolved through arbitration. The determination of arbitrability is contingent upon on the laws of the enforcing state and heavily influenced by public policy considerations, leading to differences between states. The court may refuse RAE if it reaches to a conclusion that in its jurisdiction the subject matter of the dispute is beyond the realm of arbitrability, or its public policy would prevent its enforcement (Moses, 2008).

Understanding Public Policy

The submission to any method of resolving conflicts outside the realm of state's authority was considered to be against the sovereign dignity (Anusornsen, 2012). It is on this basis the concept of public policy is largely founded. The term public policy embodies essentials concerning morality and justice of which the state is under obligation to safeguard. The forum state's legal system recognizes its laws or standards to be its public policy which might be found contrary to

either the arbitration agreement or the award. It additionally comprises norms which are deeply rooted within the countrywide legal and social shape of a society, representing its collective conscience (Baig & Fatima, 2024). A line is drawn in public policy between private and public autonomies whereby private autonomy is disregarded in the state where enforcement is pursued by way of its mandatory rules (Tosun, 2019). Each state thus finds its public policy to have been articulated through legislative enactments, constitutional limitations, or judicial practices. If the arbitration parties are determined to have egregiously violated or ignored these policies, or if an award contravenes principles of comity, judicial overreach, or respect, a domestic court may deny the award's enforcement to preserve the sanctity of its own legal framework.

The Convention'27 is seen as an inaugural framework which stipulated public policy or the principles of law to be the grounds for denying recognition or enforcement to the award in the state where it was pursued. Since the expression 'principles of law' was ambiguous and different interpretations in different jurisdictions were apprehended, it was decided against the inclusion of such expression in new convention. Be that as it may, in order to honor the sovereign rights of States and uphold widely accepted notions of justice, the 'public policy' defence was yet incorporated in sub-Article (2)(b) of Article V of the Convention'58.

Enforcement through national court procedures serves as the final recourse when parties fail to willingly adhere to an award. An award's RAE under Article V(2)(b) may be refused if on consideration by the court the same is concluded to be violating its public policy. This is known as the public policy exception ("Exception"). This exceptional defence vests in a judge the power to disregard an award that contravenes legal system of his state (Tosun, 2019). It is frequently compared to an 'unruly horse' that may result in inequitable outcomes (Ma, 2005). The English court remarked nearly two centuries ago on public policy, "it is never argued at all but where other points fail" (Redfern, et al).

As a general rule, being PE Policy of the Convention'58, awards to be final and enforceable however, subject to provided exceptions. It thus

appears PE Policy and Exception happens to present a genuine conundrum. Notwithstanding, the Exception is akin to what may be referred to as the reparative where there appears likelihood of compromising state's own very foundations in the act of RAE of an award (Tosun, 2019). Both Exception and PE Policy aims at dissipation of injustice in the sense that enforcement of unjust awards is refused in the former, while the latter does not extend to the enforcement of unjust awards (Ma, 2005).

In the international arbitration context, the concept of public policy extends beyond serving a parochial national interest (Tosun, 2019). The Convention'58 intended to restrict nations from exerting unilateral control over international trade by controlling it solely on their own terms, highlighting the necessity of reducing public policy interventions to preclude local courts from obstructing process of ICA. The majority of courts have been applying the public policy defense in accordance with the convention's PE Policy.

Approaches to Public Policy Exception

Due to the absence of its definitive explanation, each country employs its own criteria to define public policy. In general, courts in various countries tend to lean towards enforcing the Convention'58. This has been made possible by putting narrow and restrictive construction to public policy defense. Be that as it may, it is not incorrect to suggest that the national courts have interpreted it distinctively. Hence, as a necessary corollary RAE of an award are often met with difficulties in the realm of global legal diversity which will now be seen in the succeeding paragraphs.

UK

Merely an award infringes English law, its enforcement cannot be refused (Tang, 2014). The invocation of public policy may alone serve to uphold the equitable and systematic administration of justice, and cannot provide an unrestricted means to evade the execution of awards rendered under the Convention'58. [*Nigerian National Petroleum Case*] However, securing a contract via or with the intent to facilitate an unlawful conduct or deceit, including perjury, corruption, and bribery, is deemed inconsistent with the prevailing English law's public policy the RAE of which will be denied. It was ruled

in *Soleimany* case by English Court of Appeal that if the arbitrators' award is in the form of sanctioning illegal actions occurring in a nearby nation by utilizing that country's laws, then the same may not be enforced. In the *Al Khaimah National Oil case*, the Appellate Court in England and Wales asserted that public policy issues cannot be thoroughly described. The public policy dimension necessitates the demonstration of either an illegality or that the awards' enforcement will significantly jeopardize the public interest or be deemed objectionable by the typical, sensible citizen upon whom the state exerts its authority.

US

The Convention'58 aims at removing barriers to execution. The United States' strategy also aligns with PE Policy because it reckons that the foregoing aim could only be achieved by avoiding wide interpretations of public policy. The RAE of awards cannot be simply brushed aside if in applying law arbitrators erred, award is absent legal reasoning or vividly disregard of law, inconsistent testimony, or there exists economic sanctions, diplomatic relations, and existence of restrict trade clause (Tang, 2014).

Highlighting the narrow approach in construing this defence in *Parsons & Whittemore* case, the United States Court of Appeals for the Second Circuit explained that "to read the public policy defence as a parochial device protective of national political interest would seriously undermine the Convention's utility. This provision was not meant to enshrine the vagaries of international politics under the rubric of public policy." It was observed that if an award is found transcending most basis notions of morality and justice, only then for denial RAE of award public policy defence can be pressed into service.

Served as a precedent the foregoing case in *National Oil Corporation* case wherein National Oil Corporation ("Applicant"), wholly owned by Libyan Government, entered into an EPSA ("Agreement") with a Delaware Corporation, Libyan Sun Oil Company ("Company"), according to which the Company for an oil exploration activity in Libya undertook execution and financing. The Company commenced the exploratory activities. However, political tensions between the US and Libyan

governments prompted the former to order measures against the latter. The provision in the Agreement containing *force majeure* was invoked by the Company. The basis of its claim was that since travel to Libya had got restricted on the directives of US State Department, performance thus was suspended. It was followed by the Applicant's arbitration application with the ICC's Court of Arbitration in Paris, France. Following hearings, it was resolved by the Arbitral Tribunal that no *force majeure* clause could have been invoked in this case. It was further determined that, if other American firms could maintain operations in Libya by utilizing non-American personnel, the Company, as a Canadian subsidiary, could likewise meet its commitments. As a result, the decision favored Applicant over Company. The Applicant submitted a petition under Convention'58 to the U.S. District Court after failing to collect payment from Company. Award's recognition was opposed by the Company on ground of public policy, but the argument being misconceived met with no success. 'Public policy may be invoked only in the event of the enforcement of the award conflicting with the deepest notions of morals and justice of the *lex fori*', the Court observed. Reference was also made to *Parsons & Whittemore* case, wherein it was stated in relation to public policy defence that it was more than a parochial device to protect the national interest. Having set forth the reasons in its opinion, the Court recognized the award in favour of the Applicant and against the Company.

Germany

'Apart from violations of basic civil rights', stated German Court of Appeals, 'violation of a rule in connection with the basis of political or economic life would contravene public policy.' So does concepts of justice in Germany when inconsistent with award (Tosun, 2019). The Higher Regional Court of Düsseldorf similarly noted that an award contravening the fundamental principles of law, economy, and society in Germany is considered to breach public policy, rendering it unacceptable by national standards. The court elucidated that the crucial moment for evaluating a breach of German public policy was during enforcement, rather than when the award was issued or when the parties

finalized the agreements in question. The assertion of public policy was ultimately dismissed, as the Respondent did not substantiate the facts underlying its objection (New York Convention Guide).

Australia

Likewise, the Federal Court of Australia stated that the Exception in Convention'58 can only be given effect to refuse enforcement when core questions of morality and justice in the jurisdiction where enforcement is sought are involved. Hence, the PE Policy of Convention'58 was recognized in *Balaji Coke Industry* case. No wide discretion is extended under the public policy ground to the enforcement court. "It should not be", further court stated, "used to give effect to parochial and idiosyncratic tendencies of the courts of the enforcement state."

Hong Kong

Notwithstanding having ratified the Convention'58 in its national law, an award, being so objectionable to the basis notions of justice in the country where enforcement is sought, cannot be expected to be given RAE on the touchstone of public policy. This is what Hong Kong Court of Final Appeal held in *Polytek Engineering Company* case.

Canada

Nevertheless, where the parties in no unequivocal terms stipulated the requirement of reasons for an award, then non-compliance of the same has been seen a procedural breach of public policy rendering the award to be unqualified for its RAE in the enforcement state. In the case of *Smart Systems Technologies*, a Canadian court ruled that the absence of rationale in the award contravened procedural public policy. Since the parties' agreement mandated that the award includes justifications and in absence of them the court declined to recognize and enforce the award. An award not stating any reasons would be contrary to public policy not because it lacked reasons but for the reason that it was the parties' written wish that had not been taken care of. It was further observed that the courts have always a seminal role to play in a democratic structure to determine as to whether the decision is arbitrary.

The RAE of award has also been denied where interest rates and cost not proportional to awarded damages were seen contravening public policy. Reference is made to *Laminoirs v. Southwire Co.*, wherein an award based on awarded interest was denied enforcement. Paying additional interest if no payment was made in two months was held by the court usurious, thus violating its most fundamental principles of morality and justice and on the basis of Exception under Article V(2)(b) of the Convention'58, award was not enforced. Similarly, an interest rate of seventy three percent per year with daily capitalization was found by the Supreme Court of Austria to have violated basic principles of its law on debts (Tosun, 2019). According to the court, it was against the public policy and the interest should not lead to unjust enrichment of the creditor and cannot have a punitive and deterrent function.

China

Rather than refer to public policy, in Chinese legislation it is referred as 'public interest'. It is of no concern whether any party has taken the ground of public interest in the petition or not, Chinese courts have felt incumbent to consider if there is any violation of public interest (Redfern, et al). Not only include in the phrase 'public interest' the adopted rules, expressed state commitments and social morality, state's less transparent interests and unstable short-term policies are also covered under it (Tang, 2014). Breaches of basic principles of Chinese law, national sovereignty or national security, or breaches of the principles of social ethics and fundamental moral value have been stated by the Supreme People's Court to be existing in public interest (Redfern, et al). Perhaps this explains why Chinese courts refused RAE of an award made against a state company in China. The local court in the *Dongfeng Garments* case declined to enforce a decision against a corporation of considerable significance to the local economy, apprehensive that such action could undermine the state's economic authority and jeopardize its overseas trade links. The decision is no longer valid as the Supreme People's Court overturned it.

The decision in *Heavy Metal* case is also worth mentioning here. It is in direct conflict with PE Policy. The US Heavy Metal band was banned by Chinese

Ministry of Culture to perform because to their unacceptable conduct, which included drinking, smoking, lying and jumping on/off stage. The award compensating band for lost income was denied enforcement by the Supreme People's Court. This ruling was predicated on the conviction that actual circumstances were disregarded in its award by the tribunal as heavy metal performances were perceived as contrary to national feelings and misaligned with societal and public interests. This led analysts to assert that China's public policy encompasses more than just public morals, incorporating traditional and societal sentiments as well (Redfern, et al).

Pakistan

The Constitution of Islamic Republic of Pakistan, 1973 ("Constitution '73") is the paramount legal framework of the nation, establishing ultimate sovereignty in Allah Almighty over the universe and requiring elected representatives to exercise their authority within His prescribed limits, ensuring that their legislation adheres to the principles of Shariah. Any agreement or contract that contravenes Islamic law is deemed void, and the court cannot enforce any award arising from a contract that encompasses prohibited activities, such as the purchase of alcohol (Baig & Fatima, 2024). In the *Grosvenor Casine* case, the Sindh High Court underscored the importance of the Quran and the teachings (Sunnah) of the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), concluding that the government could not endorse the interest-based conditions of the award due to their inconsistency with Shariah law, nor could a foreign arbitral award supporting a claim contrary to Shariah law be acknowledged in Pakistan. It may be consistently asserted from the preceding intent that Islamic law in Pakistan serves as a source of national policy.

In Pakistan, the domain of public policy has developed primarily from contract law focused on domestic issues, and subsequently, this domestic notion of public policy was read into international awards (Rana, 2020). In Convention'58, Articles V(1)(a) and V(2)(b) provide against RAE of invalid arbitration agreement and award contravening public policy of enforcement state. Principles established for assessing the legality of general contracts in Pakistan are similarly applied to evaluate the validity of

arbitration agreements. One provision is incorporated in Section 23 of contract law, which stipulates that a contract violating public policy shall be deemed invalid and unenforceable. Another crucial aspect to consider is that in Pakistan, if the primary contract on account of public policy is rendered unlawful, the arbitration agreement contained within it will likewise be judged void. This contrasts with the separability doctrine, which posits that arbitration clauses possess an autonomous life from the primary contract, enabling their persistence even in the event of a breach of the main contract.

In *Hubco v. WAPDA* (decided by a majority of 3 to 2), the Supreme Court of Pakistan ("Supreme Court") ignored the doctrine of separability concluding that the conflicts between the parties did not pertain to commercial concerns arising from a legitimate contract, but rather challenged the legitimacy of the contract itself. It was stated that charges of corruption established grounds for additional investigation, potentially nullifying the documents. Issues pertaining to purported criminal conduct are inappropriate for arbitration according to public policy. Thus, it is for the court to give ruling for a valid contract. However, the minority view believed that it was within the power of arbitrator to investigate even allegations of corruption and to adjudge the legality or otherwise of the contract, emphasizing parties' preference for resolving their issues in this manner.

Over the last decade, there has been seen shift of Pakistan's judiciary towards PE Policy. In this regard, the decision in *Louis Dreyfus* by Lahore High Court, Lahore ("LHC") is an important one for several reasons. Firstly, the LHC recognized the PE Policy envisaged in Convention'58 which was manifestly evident in Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitration Agreement and Foreign Award Act, 2011 ("Act of 2011"), a domestic legislation to implement the Convention'58 in Pakistan. Secondly, it was stated that the courts must adhere to the legislature's intentions and comply with Convention'58 when enforcing awards. Thirdly, the LHC acknowledged the significance of the PE Policy that courts must follow when evaluating applications for RAE of awards, cautioning against its skepticism. Fourthly, the LHC underscored policy of Act of 2011 which mandates addressing disputes using the standard summary

judgment test rather than a whole trial. Last but not the least, the court noted awards are expected to be enforced under public policy and decline should only be directed if a valid reason is unequivocally demonstrated.

Following an extensive examination of both foreign and domestic jurisprudence, the *LHC* in its ruling in *Orient Power* elucidated the interpretation and extent of the public policy of Pakistan. A Gas Supply Agreement (“Supply Agreement”) was executed between Orient Power Co. (“Appellant”) and Sui Northern Gas Pipelines (“Respondent”) where the latter was to supply gas to the former. A dispute arose when the Appellant disregarded its duty to take or pay as per the Supply Agreement. The issue was resolved via arbitration at the London Court of International Arbitration. Under s.6 of the Act of 2011, application by Respondent for RAE of awards in *LHC* was filed. An objection was raised by the Appellant that the claim under the Supply Agreement contravened country’s public policy. The Appellant contended that the actual loss acknowledged by the Respondent was Rs. 356,104,346.25, while the awarded sum of Rs. 603,202,083/- constitutes the latter’s unjust enrichment, violating the principles of economic justice as enshrined in the Constitution’73. Thus, award may not be recognized in terms of Exception in Article V(2)(b) of the Convention’58. On its turn, it was apprised by the Respondent that narrow construction be applied to the Exception and given the absence of public harm, it cannot be made basis of refusal.

The *LHC* emphasized that the Convention’58 aimed at enforcement of awards with limited grounds on which it can be refused. Non-interference constitutes a fundamental policy of contracting nations, resisting public policy reasons. It was observed that the Exception ought to be invoked solely where an award affects core State’s principles. Therefore, the Exception is not to be employed as a means to evaluate the merits of an award or to read into new basis for denial under the Convention. The Supply Agreement was found to be a contractual arrangement between the parties, voluntarily negotiated and executed by the parties – enforceable in its entirety. Since no loss is caused to the public thus award was

not inconsistent with state’s public policy and the appeal stood dismissed.

The Appellant challenged *LHC*’s judgment before the Supreme Court. Amongst other grounds, it was argued by the Appellant that protection against unjust enrichment was a seminal aspect of public policy in Pakistan and award be denied recognition under Article V(2)(b) of the Convention’58. The Supreme Court did not agree with the Appellant’s argument. It stated that for a claim of unjust enrichment to succeed, there must be enrichment at the expense of the Appellant and this enrichment must be unjust in such a way that there should be no lawful justification for the same. The Respondent entitled to receive payment for the same amount of gas twice was based upon failure of the Appellant to take up the gas, the court clarified with ‘juristic reason’ for the enrichment. It was further noted that the majority of courts worldwide have embraced a stringent stance with regard to the Exception offering clarity to parties and guarantee the finality of verdicts. The public policy defense in these instances necessitates elevated evidentiary standards for the rejection of awards under it. Upheld the decision of the *LHC* in appeal, with the Supreme Court concluding in favour of award found not contravening Pakistan’s public policy.

The decision in *POSCO International Corporation* (“*POSCO*”) is yet another significant contribution in the context of the PE Policy and Exception jurisprudence in Pakistan. *POSCO* submitted, to the *LHC*, an application for RAE of an award in accordance with the Act of 2011. During the course of hearing, there was an argument that the award being against Pakistan’s public policy cannot be enforced. The *LHC* noted that interpretation of ‘public policy’ differs throughout courts worldwide, rendering it a concept devoid of a precise definition. The court associates the terms ‘notoriously slippery’ and ‘inherently imprecise’ with public policy. The expansive meaning to the term ‘public policy’ expounded by the Indian Supreme Court in *Renusagar Power Company Ltd.* and *Associated Builders* cases referred by the Respondent to refuse the application was discarded. The court observed that expanding the interpretation to public policy by Indian Supreme Court has created significant

ambiguity and has potentially obscured the distinctions between the various defenses outlined in Article V which may now be overshadowed by the defense of public policy outlined in Article V (2)(b).

The *LHC* also adopted a non-interference stance and a PE Policy alluded to in *Orient Power* by the Supreme Court. No Pakistani laws or public policies were violated as s.4 of the 2011 Act outlines the public policy. It requires parties in an arbitration agreement to refer their issues to the designated tribunals for resolution and instructs Pakistani courts to send parties to arbitration. It was also emphasized Pakistan's national policy as a contracting state is to promote arbitration and deter participation in foreign litigation. Further asserted by *LHC* that an arbitration agreement imposes a 'positive' obligation on the parties to solve disputes through arbitration, while simultaneously establishing a 'negative' undertaking that prevents them from pursuing claims within the agreement's scope in any forum other than arbitration. This attitude reinforces international contracts are upheld in Pakistani courts. The court determined that Pakistan adheres to the Constitution⁷³, with its public policy delineated by legislation passed by Parliament. An arbitration decision would be considered against public policy only if it contravenes a constitutional mandate, is expressly forbidden by law, or violates any legal stipulations, and not otherwise. Having rejected all refusal grounds including the public policy, the High Court ordered acceptance of the application seeking RAE of award.

Next important decision pertains to *Tradhol International*. An application on behalf of Tradhol International ("Applicant") was filed under s.6 of the Act of 2011 for RAE of the award. In response to which, objections under s.7 thereof were filed by Shakarganj Limited ("Respondent") wherein RAE was sought to be refused on grounds under Articles V(I)(a) and V(2)(b) of the Convention⁵⁸. It was submitted that award should not be enforced as Respondent neither signed the contract nor authorized another party to do so it contravenes the country's public policy. This argument was vehemently repelled stating that Respondent's failure to contest the email exchanges indicates the existence of the agreement and renders the objection to its validity unfounded.

The *LHC* adhered to the rationale established in judgments such as *Orient Power* and *POSCO*, recognizing PE Policy of the Convention⁵⁸. The court further stressed on the significance of upholding the trust in Pakistani courts by implementing awards, even if one party has filed a claim locally. No specific public policy proscribing the award from being enforced was brought on record by the Respondent. The court struck down the claim that public policy should deny enforcement, rejecting it being baseless and misdirected.

The decision in *Taisei Corporation* case is the authoritative pronouncement by the Supreme Court in relation to ICA for several accounts. Firstly, scope of 'foreign arbitral award' as defined in Act of 2011 came under consideration. Except for the award to be made in a state party to the Convention⁵⁸ or in another state notified by the Federal Government in the official Gazette, no further action is necessary for an award to be considered a 'foreign arbitral award' in terms of s. 2(e) of the said Act. The term 'means' used in s.2(e) thereof indicates a restrictive and exhaustive definition that precludes any additional considerations, involving the laws regulating the main contract, arbitration agreement, arbitration process, and the parties' nationalities for classifying arbitral award in the Act.

Secondly, the PE Policy of the Convention⁵⁸ was emphasized highlighting its primary aim of promoting RAE of the award with least interference and maximal efficacy. In its decision, the court attempted to contrast Convention²⁷ from the Convention⁵⁸ to emphasize the latter's PE Policy, whereby unlike the former where one party had to prove five conditions for RAE of an award, the Convention⁵⁸ permits refusal based only on the grounds in Article V thereof which the party opposing RAE has to substantiate through cogent piece of evidence. Thirdly, it was noted that the provisions relating to refusal of RAE in Article V of Convention⁵⁸ is optional rather than compulsory. The defences enumerated therein are deemed complete therefore judges are instructed to construe them restrictively, particularly public policy. Fourthly, the court greatly stressed that any interpretation of public policy which amounts to introducing grounds not enumerated in the Convention⁵⁸ cannot be sustained, including

challenging an arbitrator's decision based on legal or factual errors. Such attempt would compromise the PE Policy of the Convention'58. Last but not the least, the court stated that the public policy defence would only succeed in Pakistan should the award was found against its fundamental principles of morality and justice. It was also clarified that the court cannot examine award on merits or add new defenses not specified in the Convention'58, such as instances where arbitrator misapplied Pakistani law or rendered a result that conflicts with it.

Conclusion

Respect for party autonomy, the PE Policy and the desire for finality are the seminal factors for the court to keep in mind while making the analysis as to whether refuse RAE of award on public policy ground. So that the said ground is not pressed into service extravagantly and the courts apply a restrictive interpretation to the said ground. The RAE of awards should only be denied where it is believed that the forum state's most basic notions of morality and justice would be contravened if an order of enforcement is made. Public policy has already found its way in Pakistan in the Constitution'73 and through Parliament made statutes. An arbitral decision may be declined recognition and execution solely if it contravenes the constitutional requirements, is expressly banned by law, or contravenes the purposes of any legislation, and not on any other grounds. These principles constitute the public policy of Pakistan that must be adhered to by all relevant parties.

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